

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF IMPLEMENTING INSW (INDONESIAN NATIONAL SINGLE WINDOW SYSTEM) ON LOGISTICS DISTRIBUTION IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

INSW is an effort by the Indonesian state in its efforts encourage the smooth flow of export and import goods. The system in INSW has experienced obstacles and obstacles service users as long as this system is implemented. This research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. The research results show that the implementation of the INSW System can be categorized as smooth, because it produces a positive impact on service users. The smooth implementation of the INSW System has been proven by several data which strengthens the opinion that the INSW System has a positive impact regarding the smooth flow of goods. The INSW system plays a very important role in facilitating the flow of export goods and import. The INSW system makes port and customs clearance easier process export and import documents because the data entered by the Exporter/Importer has been selected by the INSW System, thereby producing valid and fast data in the handling process.

Index Terms: Logistics, Export, Import, Indonesian National Single Window System.

INTRODUCTION

Trading is one of the business activities. The definition of business is broader than trade, because business covers more issues than trade, i.e. covers investment, production, marketing and others, meanwhile Trading is just one of the important activities of a business related to transactions of goods and services. However, trade is the core of business activities, because at Ultimately, every business activity culminate in an activity Trading is essentially buying and selling. No country can meet all the needs of the community himself (Sasono 2013:1).

In order for a country to meet its domestic needs, it requires the resources and industry of other countries to enable social and industrial life to run. These oppurnity are used by business actors for carrying out buying and selling transactions between countries benefit. These activities called international trade involves buying and selling activities between individuals country with other countries. One way for Indonesia to engage in international trade is to join the ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA).

Joining Indonesia at AFTA demands handling free trade issues include Export and import quickly and responsively. Problems that are often encountered in handling imported goods are hampered by the delivery process goods, as well as the number of documents required completed by the importer. According to Widjiyanto (2015), who is chairman of the logistics and forwarder association Indonesia as quoted by Gera, the number of permits in ministries and institutions countries that entrepreneurs must process makes the time spent slow and negative impact on domestic trade.

This is a problem that must be a challenge for the government to provide related solutions frequent problems of time and cost efficiency often faced by importers and domestic trading services. In 2008 the Indonesian government implemented the National Single Window (NSW) which is expected to be a solution that can make things easier for exporters and importers because document and licensing processing is done online.

The National Single Window (NSW) implemented by Indonesia is a liaison system between relevant agencies in the implementation of exports and imports as well as in domestic trade. National Single Window (NSW) is a system that allows single delivery of data and information, as well as single and synchronous decision making and production. Single decision to grant customs permits and release goods (Purwito 2015:144)

The INSW system is a system electronics related to data processing import and export to make things easier smooth licensing documents, both for exporters, Importers and customs officers. This is Convenience due to previous document processing done manually. INSW then Export/Import document processing can be done electronically. System Implementation INSW is carried out through Portal operations INSW.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The type of research used in This research is classified as research qualitative descriptive. According to Zuriah (2009:47), Descriptive research is research that directed to provide an overview of symptoms, facts, or events systematically and accurately, regarding the characteristics of the population. This research contains a description of implementation INSW System. Qualitative research is research that produces results unattainable discoveries by using statistical procedures or by means of quantification. Researcher using qualitative descriptive research to explain the implementation of the INSW System and conducting case studies in 2 large ports in Indonesia, namely Tanjung Priok, Jakarta and Tanjung Perak, Surabaya.

Customs with conduct in-depth interviews with parties officers in charge of the INSW System and para INSW System service users. Research result presented in pictorial form implementation of the obtained INSW System researchers through interviews and quotations from the results of data collection in the field This research uses two data sources namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained from the source, observed and recorded for the first time the company that is the object of research.

Data The primers in this research were obtained through interviews with Exporters, Importers, PPJK (Customs Services Management Entrepreneur) as well as officer who handles the INSW System. Data source obtained by researchers indirectly through intermediary media. In this research data the secondary used is documentation as well other data that supports this research. The data taken is data that related to the implementation and role of the System INSW at KPPBC Tanjung Customs Intermediate Type Perak Surabaya. Data collection methods in research these are interviews, observations, documentation and triangulation.

DISCUSSION

Before implementing the INSW System, Customs officers, importers/exporters, as well as the agency issuing import export permits carries out long process in handling documents export and import. First step, Importer must download the PIB module whose function is to assist users in creating PIB document. Then, the importer prepares documents that must be submitted to the Customs Office Excise tax in hard copy form. The document must be submitted directly to Customs officers Excise that specifically serves import documents.

After the INSW System is implemented, the importer does not need to provide permission imports from related agencies (GA) and hand it over directly to the Customs officer Excise. This is because of the agencies the import permit provider (GA) has input the permit that they issue regarding certain importers on the INSW System. So, the officers didn't need to wait for the Importer regarding permission, however officers can check directly on the INSW System whether the permit issuing agency has issued it import permit or not. So the document Imports can be processed immediately so they can be completed faster.

Before the INSW System was implemented, INSW officers found it difficult to identify what permit issuing agency export/import has been whether or not to issue permission to the party Relevant Exporter/Importer. First, processing Documents can take around 3 days. Now that the INSW System is implemented, document processing just takes time just a few hours. Based on free trade theory according to Amir (2004:203) is an economic concept regarding inter-commerce transaction traffic country carried out without hindrance.

This matter shows that goods traffic between countries no longer burdened with import duties, system quotas and complicated customs procedures and convoluted. So referring to this theory, in order to face AEC 2015, preparation Indonesia is reflected in the readiness of the INSW System in carrying out its functions in accordance with its objectives.

Fundamental obstacles before the INSW System implementation for officers is difficult to identify the authenticity of export/import permits that has been issued so that the service given takes a long time. Meanwhile, for service users, it is waste costs, energy and time to process documents export/import because you have to come directly to

agency issuing export/import permits and then must come directly to the Customs Office in framework for submitting and processing documents.

Permission issued by the competent authorities already there is no doubt about its authenticity. INSW System makes it easier for Customs to declare validity and correctness of the data (related to the number and type of goods), both related to export licensing and imported, so it's safer. INSW System makes it easier for Customs and Excise to process licensing because now it has been verified by the system, unlike before.

Before the INSW System existed, because there was no integrated access with other agencies, documents deposited by Exporters/Importers were prone to being falsified. This is because the data deposited is in the form of hardcopy which is easy to change. Thus, the INSW System is very helpful, Customs can serve it more quickly and Customs can certify the validity and the correctness of data related to export and import permits because their validity is beyond doubt.

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The costs incurred by service users are relatively reduced by implementing the INSW System. Exporters and importers do not need to come directly to the permit issuing office exports and imports are related, but can be accessed directly on the INSW website whether the agency issuing the export/import permit has issued the permit. For Exporters/Importers, with the implementation of the INSW System, the costs incurred can be minimized and it is not as frequent as before (before the implementation of the INSW System) to come directly to the Tanjung Perak Customs Intermediate Type KPPBC in order to data processing, so that interaction with officers can be reduced. This saves time and energy for both parties (officers and service users).

This research strengthens the theory put forward by Ratna (2010:14) that The Indonesia National Single Window (INSW) was implemented to speed up the flow of goods at ports and provide several benefits, such as increasing the effectiveness and performance of export-import traffic management and minimizing export-import time and costs. Some of these benefits were clearly reflected when researchers interviewed service users. The majority of service users feel benefited and made easier by implementing the INSW System

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Services carried out by Customs and Excise can be faster compared to before the INSW System was implemented. Customs and Excise can serve more quickly compared to before the INSW System was implemented, where processing of permit documents was done manually. Speed export/import document processing benefits exporters and importers because export/import goods will not accumulate at the port for too long.

This research is also in accordance with the theory put forward by Hamdani (2012: 38), where he states that one aspect of exports at a macro level is encouraging the development of science and technology (Science and Technology) and HR (Human Resources).

The INSW system increases para capabilities service users in interacting with electronic systems where previously export/import document handling was done manually. The more often service users access the INSW Portal, the more their ability to access it will increase. In this way, mistakes previously made will decrease as you get used to accessing the INSW portal. User Services can get the latest information when accessing the INSW portal, so they will be smarter in carrying out their export/import activities.

Some technical problems occasionally occur with the INSW System. These problems include the loading process on the system sometimes being slow and the system access speed sometimes not being optimal. So for the new system, this is still very reasonable considering that it still needs to be improved so that the INSW System can work as perfect as expected. The role of the INSW System in efforts to encourage the smooth flow of export and import goods is reflected in the volume of exports and imports which tends to increase compared to before the INSW System was implemented. The INSW system, which was implemented starting in 2010, has had a positive impact on service users, officers and agencies related to export and import permits.

Starting from 2010 until now, the INSW System is considered to have successfully carried out its role so that the flow of exports and imports is smoother and more efficient. Before the INSW System was implemented, namely in 2008 and 2009, export volume and imports tend to be in a low volume position the same. Differences can be seen after the INSW System was implemented, namely from 2010 to now. The differences are in number the volume of exports and imports tends to increase. This research strengthens the theory from Hamdani (2012:38) that one of the macro aspects of imports is increasing people's and government income.

The role of the INSW System in facilitating the flow of exported and imported goods has an impact on people's income, especially export/import actors, and the government in relation to import and export duties obtained from export/import actors. These costs increase along with the convenience felt after implementing the INSW System. Export/import activities of business people are increasing, resulting in prosperity society is achieved.

CONCLUSION

Implementation of the INSW System can be done categorized as smooth and on target. The INSW system plays a very important role in facilitating the flow of export goods and import. After the INSW System was implemented, both exporters, importers, PPJK, officers who handle documents, and related agencies felt benefited greatly. This is illustrated through the statements of all parties during the interviews.

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